

D7.6 - Dissemination Plan

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Control sheet

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
5G-IANA	5G for Intelligent Automotive Network Applications
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOEP	Automotive Open Experimental Platform
API	Application Programming Interface
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LTE	Long-Term Evolution
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
NF	Network Function
PU	Public Utility
SACBT	Situational Awareness in Cross-Border Road Tunnel Accidents
SME	Small & Medium Enterprise
TS	Telekom Slovenije
UC	Use Case
VNF	Virtualised Network Function
WG	Working Group

WP	Work Package
Dx.y.	Deliverable x.y.

Executive Summary

D7.6 Dissemination Plan defines the dissemination strategy and the plan of action that will be implemented by the 5G-IANA consortium to ensure that the project and its results are effectively communicated throughout the project's lifecycle. It identifies the project's target audiences, describes the methods, tools and channels that will be employed and serves as a reference point for the activities planned and the role undertaken by the project partners. Moreover, it sets the success criteria for the evaluation of the dissemination activities performed per year. Complementary, the deliverable includes the procedures to be followed for dissemination activities carried out by consortium partners.

D7.6 is a public deliverable of this project, carried out as part of 5G-IANA's WP7 '*Dissemination, exploitation, standardisation and liaison activities*' and additionally includes information about the project's scope and objectives as well as the description of WP7 to ensure that no prior knowledge related to the project, the DoA and the other WP7 deliverables is requested from the reader. Overall, it is based on, and is consistent with the DoA and the GA, but is not a substitute for reading these documents. Another version has predated the current one. The first version was submitted in February 2022, at an early stage of the project when significant results for dissemination were not produced yet. The current version 2.0 has been developed after the corrective actions requested by the EC experts in the 1st review (based on the review report received on July 2022). It provides a shorter but comprehensive description of the dissemination strategy, a more targeted dissemination plan with updated activities and target values and additional dissemination activities (videos, open calls, hackathon) to attract and engage third-party experimenters.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. 5G-IANA concept and approach

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third-party experimenters, i.e., Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. An Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP) will be specified, as the whole set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced NetApp Toolkit tailored to the Automotive sector. 5G-IANA will expose to experimenters secured and standardised Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA will target various virtualization technologies integrating dissimilar Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks for enabling the deployment of the end-to-end network services across different domains (vehicles, road infrastructure, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud resources). 5G-IANA NetApp toolkit will be linked with a new Automotive Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) Repository including an extended list of ready to use open accessible Automotive-related VNFs and NetApp templates, that will form a repository for SMEs to use and develop new applications.

Finally, 5G-IANA will develop a Distributed Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning (AI/ML) (DML) framework, that will provide functionalities for simplified management and orchestration of collections of AI/ML service components and will allow ML-based applications to penetrate the Automotive world, due to its inherent privacy preserving nature. 5G-IANA will be demonstrated through 7 Automotive-related use cases in 2 5G Stand Alone (SA) testbeds. Moving beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA will perform a multi-stakeholder cost-benefit analysis that will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models supporting a long-term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as key advanced Automotive services enabler.

1.2. WP7 Dissemination, exploitation, standardisation and liaison activities

WP7 is an integral part of the project and will run in parallel with the other work packages throughout the project's lifecycle, to bring high visibility to 5G-IANA activities and outcomes to the wider public and key stakeholders.

The main objectives of WP7 are to:

- Define and implement the overall dissemination and communication strategy and plan for soundly promoting the progress and outputs of 5G-IANA and increasing awareness;
- Develop the necessary and impactful brand identity and communication materials and tools for targeted promotion, to ensure mainstreaming of project's results to a wide range of stakeholders at various geographical levels and relevant sectors;
- Circulating project advancements and results to key stakeholders and ensuring the widest diffusion of the project's outcomes, helping to achieve the vision and strategy for 5G-PPP Phase 3;
- Coordinate the scientific outreach through the development of open access papers and participation in scientific and industrial events;
- Liaise with relevant R&D projects, already established organisations/associations and networks, standardisation bodies and organisations to ensure knowledge exchange, interoperability of the developed systems as well as wide market penetration;
- Develop the necessary methodology and assist partners in the preparation of homogeneous and effective exploitation plans for 5G-IANA.

The WP7 for '*Dissemination, exploitation, standardisation and liaison activities*' consists of five tasks (as foreseen in the DoA), and each one is led by a project partner (Task Leader), who will be supported by one or more partners involved in WP7 or with resources in that particular task, and 11 deliverables deliverables (Annex 5 - WP7 Deliverables). All WP7 tasks are interrelated and complementary, thus they are aligned under the supervision of WP7 Leader, VICOM. In Annex 3 - WP7 tasks and leaders, the WP7 tasks, their leaders and their description are outlined.

1.3. D7.6 Dissemination Plan

1.3.1. Purpose of the deliverable

The **D7.6 Dissemination Plan** is carried out as part of 5G-IANA's WP7 and specifically Task 7.2 Dissemination Activities and Events. The purpose of D7.6 is to outline the project's dissemination plan and to act as a reference point for 5G-IANA partners by providing a clear overview of the opportunities and activities connected with WP7 and Task 7.2 in particular. The document specifies the details regarding 5G-IANA's dissemination strategy and roadmap, while also identifying the main dissemination activities to be performed by the 5G-IANA consortium during the project's lifecycle. In addition, it is designed to serve as a supportive framework for project partners, by listing relevant dissemination channels (i.e., target conferences and journals), clearly defining the internal procedures to be followed, as well as the specific metrics (Key Performance Indicators, KPIs) for assessing the success of performed activities. The deliverable is dynamic and will therefore be regularly evaluated and updated to ensure its alignment with the progress of the overall project activities and potential external changes.

1.3.2. Structure of the deliverable

Chapter one of this dissemination plan starts with an introduction to 5G-IANA, the role of WP7 in the project and the purpose of the deliverable. **Chapter two** develops the dissemination strategy and roadmap. Additionally, the procedure of reporting and assessing the dissemination activities is presented. **Chapter three** describes how this strategy will be implemented. It presents detailed information around targeted events, conferences, journals and lists the plan for the dissemination activities from 2022 through 2024. The conclusion forms the **last chapter**. The deliverable also includes a set of annexes, where the approval procedures, WP7 tasks and leaders, WP7 partner participation, performed activities and a list of the WP7 deliverables are presented.

1.3.3. Intended Readership

This deliverable is public (PU dissemination level) and therefore is intended for consortium partners, including the European Commission (funding authority), as well as individuals who are interested in getting more information about the 5G-IANA project.

1.3.4. Relation of D7.6 to other WP7 deliverables

Communication and Dissemination are integral parts of a project and crucial for its success and long-lasting effect. Therefore, respective strategies and plans should be established at the early stages of the project to lead project partners through the process and strengthen engagement in WP7 activities.

Three separate documents have been created as foreseen in the DoA:

- a) D7.2 Communication strategy and plan [1];
- b) D7.4 Communication tools [2], and
- c) D7.6 Dissemination plan.

The aforementioned documents are interrelated, but not overlapping. More specifically, **D7.2 Communication strategy and plan** focuses on the communication activities that will maximise the project's public awareness and visibility and defines the overall strategy and plan for communication, dissemination and liaison activities. Then, **D7.4 Communication tools** describes the development and the available communication tools to be used for promoting 5G-IANA. Finally, the **D7.6 Dissemination plan** provides an initial dissemination strategy and sets the KPIs, describes the channels and tools to be deployed and provides an initial list of the planned activities to disseminate the project's results and outcomes.

2. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY AND OBJECTIVES

This section includes the main aspects of 5G-IANA's dissemination strategy, including the objectives, the stakeholders to whom the external dissemination actions will be addressed to (2.1.1), the tools and channels (2.1.2) that will be used by the consortium to diffuse the project's key messages and findings, and finally, the **six dissemination indicators** (2.2.1) for measuring the project's dissemination performance.

The specific and main objective of Task 7.2 Dissemination Activities and Events, as defined in the project's Grant Agreement is to ensure that the 5G-IANA results are systematically disseminated to the expert communities and to relevant stakeholders throughout the lifetime of the project.

2.1.1. Dissemination Objectives and Target Audience

The dissemination strategy has been developed to achieve the following objectives:

- Ensure the production and **publication of scientific and technical papers** from the 5G-IANA experts in conference proceedings and top ranked peer-reviewed scientific and technology journals and raise awareness of the project's novel scientific and research results;
- Ensure visibility and a **good scientific reputation** for the project, achieving maximum outreach to key stakeholders (especially SMEs), also contributing to the promotion of Europe as leader in 5G technology, as well as to the sustainability of the project;
- Organise, participate in and engage stakeholders in **various digital and physical events** to showcase the project's activities and results;
- **Reach out to third-parties** (i.e., experimenters outside of the consortium), to engage them in onboarding and validating their Application Functions/Network Functions (AFs/NFs)/NetApps on the 5G-IANA Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP);
- To keep stakeholders and partners informed on **progress** made and **milestones** reached;
- Establish and maintain **cooperation with relevant 5G PPP projects** and other 5G initiatives and bodies.

The identification and detailed definition of relevant actors and targeted communities (see Section 2.2, 'D7.2 Communication strategy and plan') to whom the dissemination

actions should be addressed to is critical for disseminating information and results in a targeted and effective manner. The ‘target groups’ identified for 5G-IANA’s dissemination activities are the following:

- **Industry:** ICT & software suppliers; infrastructure suppliers; telecommunication operators, information providers, OEMs, cloud operators, etc.
- **Institutions:** policy and decision makers at European and national level; standardisation bodies; national or regional funding bodies, etc.
- **Scientific and Research community:** academic and research centres; operators of test sites and living labs to integrate piloted technologies for future applications, etc.
- **End users:** sector SMEs and start-ups in the automotive and telecom sectors; user groups impacted by developed technologies; end-user associations, etc.

2.1.2. Dissemination Tools and Channels

The impact of the dissemination activities will be amplified through a set of specific tools and channels. 5G-IANA will employ the following tools for effectively disseminating the project’s developments and results:

- **Scientific and technical papers:** Papers in conference proceedings and journals, technical reports, white papers, etc.;
- **Presentations in conferences and external events:** Oral and poster presentations, special sessions, panel discussions, webinars and workshops;
- **Videos:** related to the overall project, the demonstrations, as well as the project’s developments and activities;
- **Trade shows and exhibitions:** fairs and exhibitions around Europe and globally, to present the project’s progress and also to get in touch with potential future customers;
- **Project events:** the project will organise 3 events, including 2 demo events (a major one where all UCs will be demonstrated at the NOKIA 5G testbed and a smaller one enabling the NOKIA testbed and the Telekom Slovenije 5G testbed where only UC7-SACBT will be demonstrated) as well as the Final Project Event;
- **5G-IANA webinars:** webinars will be organised by the 5G-IANA consortium or jointly with other ICT-41 or 5G-PPP projects to reach people who have a stated interest in the project’s work and engage external experimenters;
- **Hackathon:** planned to take place during M35/M36 to disseminate the 5G-IANA solutions to entities willing to enter the Automotive-related 5G-enabled services;

- **Community meetings and collaboration:** participation in cross-ICT-41 meetings, leverage opportunities for cross-project dissemination, liaise with and advertise within the 5G-PPP WGs [e.g., *Pre-Standardization Trials, Vision and Societal Challenges (BVME SG), Architecture, 5G for CAM, Software Networks, SME WG, Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation (TMV)*] and other collaboration activities with e.g., 5G-AA, Incubator Politecnico (LINKS), ERTICO, 5G Turbo Acceleration Programme, External Advisory Board (EAB) members, 5G-IANA's project officer for dissemination through EU channels, etc.;
- **5G-IANA website:** the [5G-IANA website](#) [3] will include blogposts written by partners, public deliverables, publications (*pre-prints or openly accessible publications*), presentations, project activities such as organization of 5G-IANA events/webinars, links from the established dissemination synergies with similar projects and initiatives as well as news from any performed joint activities with them. The website will also be the main tool for advertising (and soliciting the interest regarding) the two Open Calls to third-parties that the project will arrange;
- **5G-IANA social media:** Within the context of promoting the project results widely and effectively, the project's social media accounts on [LinkedIn](#) [4] and [Twitter](#) [5] will also be utilised with constant updates about publications, events, presentations and other dissemination activities performed by the consortium.
- **Zenodo:** The [5G-IANA Zenodo Community](#) has been created in M14 of the project. The scope of this community is to make freely available and under open access status all public deliverables, scientific publications and publicly available results of the 5G-IANA H2020 Project.

2.1.3. Dissemination Roadmap

During the first months of the project, the aim of the dissemination activities was to generally inform target stakeholders about the project's main objectives and expected outcomes and results.

More specifically, the informative [flyer](#) has been designed (M06) to be widely disseminated online and at events, while the project has already been featured in the [5G PPP Phase 3 projects' brochure](#) (M01). The project's [roll-up banner](#) and general [poster](#) were designed (M14) to be used for internal meetings and external events and the first professional video was created (M17) to be launched in the European Commission stand at the TRA 2022 Conference in Lisbon, Portugal.

Moreover, the 5G-IANA consortium has already (M17) participated in five (5) paper publications, two (2) joint white papers, one (1) poster presentation, six (6) presentations, two (2) Special Interest Sessions and one (1) exhibition booth (Annex 6 – List of Performed Activities). As more results become available from the second year of the project, partners are regularly encouraged to disseminate them through technical papers, workshops, webinars, presentations etc.

The 5G-IANA consortium will also leverage dissemination tools to promote the 5G-IANA AOEP 1st release (M24), provide a description of the repositories (NetApp toolkit), the business-related benefits from using the platform, as well as a presentation of the NOKIA and Telecom Slovenia testbeds and their facilities' offerings. A strong effort will be given to press releases and media involvement, as well as to webinars and/or consultation workshops, so as to widely transmit the 5G-IANA messages and developments to the target audiences and engage relevant stakeholders such as third-party experimenters and SMEs. Finally, technical papers presenting the final results of 5G-IANA will be published at various International and European scientific conferences (see 3.2.1) and scientific journals (see 3.3.2), while demonstrations of the available solutions will be showcased at relevant events and exhibitions.

2.2. Monitoring and Reporting of Dissemination Activities

The performed dissemination activities throughout the project's lifecycle, as described within this deliverable, will be monitored as well as constantly discussed and evaluated amongst the consortium. The monitoring system will provide evidence on whether the 5G-IANA Dissemination Plan is being implemented as initially foreseen. It will also assist in identifying possible implementation obstacles and assess whether further actions are required to ensure that objectives are met. In order to maximise the impact and tractability of the project's dissemination activities, the success criteria of this Dissemination Plan are focused on quantitative measurements.

2.2.1. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

For measuring and evaluating the effectiveness of the dissemination plan and the success of the project's activities, the following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been set (The KPIs' target values in the current D7.6 version have been updated, to better reflect the project's capacity and extended duration.

Table 1, Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)), indicating a target value for each dissemination tool, channel, and activity per year.

The KPIs' target values in the current D7.6 version have been updated, to better reflect the project's capacity and extended duration.

Table 1, Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Tool/Channel	Key Performance Indicator	Target Value (per year)			
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3 *	Total
Events	Project events (Participants per event)	-	>70	>100	>100
	Conference Presentations (including paper and poster presentations)	>5	>12	>16	>33
	Exhibition Stands	>1	>2	>3	>6
	Webinars (number of webinars/participants)	1/40	5/40	3/40	9
Publications	Scientific Publications (including journal publications, papers in conference proceedings and white papers)	>3	>8	>10	>21
	Trade Magazines & Non-Scientific Publications	>1	>3	>3	>7
Other	Videos	-	>2	>8	>10
	Open Calls	-	1	1	2
	Hackathon	-	-	1	1

* Y3 column includes all the produced results (*performance*) until the completion of 5G-IANA lifecycle, including the project's extension, i.e., M25 – M42.

2.2.1. Reporting and Monitoring Activities

The 5G-IANA dissemination activities will be reported periodically (periodic reports) and towards the end of the project in **D7.8 – Report on the dissemination activities** (M36) for the presentation of all dissemination activities carried out during the project's lifetime. The report will assess the different dissemination activities, especially partners' efforts to promote the project in various conferences, journals, workshops, seminars or meetings.

It will also include results of the demo and final events. To record all activities past, present and future, an online reporting tool has been established on Redmine, the project's collaborative tool.

Partners will contribute to the dissemination reporting by submitting a dissemination request by e-mail to the T7.2 Leader (Sevi Christoforou - ICCS) as specified in the Dissemination Procedure (Annex 1 - Dissemination and Approval Procedure) and by filling in a dissemination report (Annex 2 - Dissemination Activities Report template) that will be sent once the dissemination activity is completed.

3. DISSEMINATION PLAN AND ACTIVITIES

3.1. Project Events and Demos

The project will organise **3 events**, including 2 demo events, one in Ulm (Germany) and one in Ljubljana (Slovenia), as well as the Final Project Event presenting the vision and strategy of 5G-PPP, and also to efficiently showcase the project's progress to multiple stakeholders.

3.1.1. Demo Events

5G-IANA will utilise 2 different 5G SA (Standalone Access) test networks. One in the City of **Ulm** (Germany) operated by NOKIA where all Use Cases (UCs) will be demonstrated and one in **Ljubljana** (Slovenia) operated by TELEKOM SLOVENIJE where the UC7 '*Situational Awareness in Cross Border Road Tunnel Accidents*' will be demonstrated [Figure 1].

NOKIA

Ulm, Germany

TELEKOM SLOVENIJE

Ljubljana, Slovenia

Figure 1, 5G-IANA's Demo Events: Ulm and Ljubljana

Demonstration leaders will be responsible for the organisation of the demonstration events with the support of the WP7 team. Press releases (both in English and in the local language of the two trial sites) will be issued prior and after the event and a media conference will be organised during the event to ensure maximum stakeholder engagement. In M20 5G-IANA will host a webinar to present the test sites at NOKIA and Telecom Slovenia, as well as the (autonomous) vehicles/OBUs/RSUs features of each site. Moreover, 5G-IANA aims to create short videos (see 3.3.4) showcasing and describing each use case demonstrated during the events. The press releases, webinar and videos will be uploaded on the website, to be widely promoted on social media, within the 5G-PPP community and through the project partners' networks.

3.1.1.1. DEMO IN ULM, GERMANY

NOKIA operates a 5G test network in Ulm, Germany. The on-air testbed consists of 5 sites – with 3 radio cells each – which cover an area of more the 100 km², including a motorway (A8), a highway (B10), a high-speed train line (S21) and major parts of the city of Ulm. The seven automotive-related use cases that will be demonstrated are the following:

- **UC1:** Remote Driving
- **UC2:** Manoeuvres Coordination for Autonomous Driving
- **UC3:** Virtual Bus Tour
- **UC4:** AR Content Delivery for Vehicular Networks
- **UC5:** Parking Circulation & High-Risk Driving Hotspot Detection
- **UC6:** Network Status Monitoring
- **UC7:** Situational Awareness in Cross-Border Road Tunnel Accidents

3.1.1.2. DEMO IN LJUBLJANA, SLOVENIA

TELEKOM SLOVENIJE will provide a dedicated 5G infrastructure located at its premises in Ljubljana for the purpose of the 5G-IANA project demonstrations and will also serve as a future 5G environment for TS. The infrastructure consists of a cloud and virtualisation environment with network connectivity through a 5G radio access network and a 5G ready core network based on EPC extensions. UC7 will be demonstrated in collaboration with NOKIA and TS testbeds.

3.1.2. Final Event

In the last year of the project, a 5G-IANA Final Event will be hosted by one of the partners, attracting about 100 relevant stakeholders. During the event, the 5G-IANA final findings and lessons learned will be presented. A press release will be issued prior the event, while journalists will be also invited to the event for a media conference and to experience first-hand the project results through demos and interviews with consortium members. To secure wide after-event dissemination, the material i.e., the press release and the technical presentations will be made available through a dedicated page on the 5G-IANA website, while a video will be created and promoted through every available channel.

3.2. Targeted Conferences, Events and Journals

Within the lifetime of the project, several 5G-IANA presentations and demonstrations will be organised at relevant conferences and events, to broadly disseminate the project's findings and outcomes. In the following sub-chapters, the relevant events where the consortium will focus their efforts to, will be presented. Moreover, 5G-IANA will be disseminated through papers in prominent journals and conference proceedings. Table 2 and Table 3 below present a compilation of opportunities in leading conferences and events as well as scientific journals and technical magazines in the fields of telecommunications, transport & mobility and 5G innovations. The selection was based on the individual plans collected by different partners and on other available opportunities that fulfil criteria in terms of focus areas and themes, location and place of activity, audience involvement and overall reputation. In the course of the project, more suitable opportunities will arise and be seized.

3.2.1. Targeted Conferences and Events

5G-IANA partners will take part in local (national), EU and global level conferences, industry trade events and exhibitions in order to raise awareness around the project activities and expected results and disseminate the relevant advancements and outcomes. In Table 2 an initial list of the targeted conferences is presented.

Table 2, Targeted Conferences

No.	Conference	About the Conference
1.	IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF'22)	<p>The IEEE Future Networks World Forum (formerly 5G World Forum) aims to bring experts from industry, academia, and research to exchange their vision as well as their achieved advances towards future networks of 5G and beyond and encourage innovative cross-domain studies, research, early deployment and large-scale pilot showcases that address the challenges of future networks.</p> <p>Link: https://fnwf.ieee.org/</p>
2.	Mobile World Congress (Barcelona)	<p>MWC Barcelona is the world's most influential event for the connectivity industry. It's where world-leading companies and trailblazers share the latest thought leadership about the progression and future of connectivity. Moreover, it is one of the best places for networking opportunities with mobile and tech industry influencers.</p> <p>Link: https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/</p>
3.	EuCNC & 6G Summit	<p>The European Conference on Networks and Communications and 6G (EuCNC & 6G Summit), combines two successful conferences in the telecommunications area: EuCNC, supported by the European Commission, and the 6G Summit, originating from the 6G Flagship programme in Finland, a pioneering programme in its area.</p> <p>The conference, with the support of the IEEE Communications Society and the European Association for Signal Processing, focuses on relevant topics in telecommunications, including communications systems and networks, experimentation and implementation and services and applications in the areas of 5G, mobile IoT and 6G.</p> <p>Link: https://www.eucnc.eu/</p>
4.	ITS Congresses	<p>The ITS Congress is the biggest event focused on smart mobility and the digitalisation of transport and is organised every year by ERTICO. The congresses are the yearly celebration of smart mobility; they underline the importance of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), particularly in cities and regions where they are hosted, and are important channels to raise awareness of smart mobility solutions among policy makers, experts and the general public. They include live sessions where industry experts present the latest</p>

		<p>developments in ITS, a showcase of cutting-edge technology and an exhibition space.</p> <p>Links: ITS World Congress: https://itsworldcongress.com/ ITS EU Congress: https://itseuropeancongress.com/ ITS America: https://www.itsamericaevents.com/</p>
5.	IEEE INFOCOM	<p>IEEE INFOCOM is a top-ranked conference on networking in the research community. It is a major conference venue for researchers to present and exchange significant and innovative contributions and ideas in the field of networking and closely related areas. IEEE INFOCOM covers both theoretical and systems research. For INFOCOM 2022, the conference includes a main technical program, a number of workshops, a keynote speech, panels, a student poster session, and demo/poster sessions.</p> <p>Link: https://infocom2022.ieee-infocom.org/</p>
6.	IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)	<p>IEEE ICC is one of two IEEE Communications Society's flagship conferences (ICC and GLOBECOM). Each year, close to 2,000 attendees from over 70 countries attend IEEE ICC to take advantage of a program which consists of exciting keynote sessions, robust technical paper sessions, innovative tutorials and workshops, and engaging industry sessions. This 5-day event is known for bringing together audiences from both industry and academia to learn about the latest research and innovations in communications and networking technology, share ideas and best practices, and collaborate on future projects.</p> <p>Link: https://icc2022.ieee-icc.org/</p>
7.	IEEE GLOBECOM	<p>IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM) is one of the IEEE Communications Society's two flagship conferences dedicated to driving innovation in nearly every aspect of communications. Each year, more than 3000 scientific researchers submit proposals for program sessions to be held at the annual conference. After extensive peer review, the best of the proposals gets selected for the conference program, which includes technical papers, tutorials, workshops and industry sessions designed specifically to advance technologies, systems and infrastructure that are continuing to reshape the world and provide all users with access to an unprecedented spectrum of high-speed, seamless and cost-effective global telecommunications services.</p>

		Link: https://globecom2022.ieee-globecom.org/
8.	Transport Research Arena (TRA)	<p>TRA, the Transport Research Arena, is the largest European research and technology conference on transport and mobility. TRA offers a great venue for researchers, policy makers and industry representatives to get together and contribute to the discussion on how research and innovation can reshape the transport and mobility system. The conference provides a unique opportunity to hear about mobility trends in different parts of Europe, learn from achievements in industry as well as share best practices of policies and deployments.</p> <p>Link: https://traconference.eu/about-tra/</p>
10.	IEEE 5G for CAM	<p>This 5G for CAM conference brings together a variety of EU-funded projects in the area of CAM, to share their experiences and present results with a view towards deployment. As Horizon 2020 is open to international participation, the event will also provide an opportunity to address a broader global perspective.</p> <p>Link: http://5gsummit.org/CAM/</p>
11.	IEEE Conference on Vehicular Technology (VTC)	<p>The IEEE Vehicular Technology Society (VTS) hosts several conferences each year so that scientists, engineers, students, technicians, and others who are interested in advancing research and development in vehicular technology and mobile networks may exchange ideas in an enjoyable and stimulating environment.</p> <p>Link: https://events.vtsociety.org/vtc2022-spring/</p>
12.	IEEE Vehicular Networking Conference (VNC)	<p>Vehicular networking and communication systems is an area of significant importance in our increasingly connected and mobile world. Effective vehicular connectivity techniques can significantly enhance efficiency of travel, reduce traffic incidents and improve safety, mitigate the impact of congestion, and overall provide a more comfortable experience. Towards this goal, the IEEE Vehicular Networking Conference (VNC) seeks to bring together researchers, professionals, and practitioners to present and discuss recent developments and challenges in vehicular networking technologies, and their applications.</p> <p>Link: https://ieee-vnc.org/2021/</p>
13.	IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC)	<p>The IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC) is an annual flagship conference of the IEEE Intelligent Transportation</p>

		<p>Systems Society (ITSS). Researchers, engineers, practitioners, and students, from industry, universities and government agencies are invited to present their latest work and to discuss research and applications for intelligent vehicles and vehicle-infrastructure cooperation. ITSC welcomes articles in the field of intelligent vehicles dealing with new developments in theory and applications, vehicle technologies and demonstrations. It also welcomes proposals for workshops and tutorial sessions to be offered the day before the symposium.</p> <p>Link: https://ieee-itss.org/conf/itsc/</p>
14.	IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS)	<p>IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS) is a conference and exhibition dedicated to approaches and technical solutions related to network management.</p> <p>Link: https://noms2022.ieee-noms.org/</p>
15.	IFIP Networking Conference	<p>IFIP Networking Conference is technically sponsored by the IFIP Technical Committee on Communication Systems (TC6). The main objectives of this conference are to bring together members of the networking community from both academia and industry, to discuss recent advances in the broad and quickly-evolving fields of computer and communication networks, and to highlight key issues, identify trends, and develop visions for the networking domain.</p> <p>Link: https://networking.ifip.org/</p>
16.	IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)	<p>IEEE WCNC is the world premier wireless event that brings together industry professionals, academics, and individuals from government agencies and other institutions to exchange information and ideas on the advancement of wireless communications and networking technology.</p> <p>Link: http://www.ieee-wcnc.org/</p>
17.	ACM/IEEE Symposium on Architectures for Networking and Communications Systems	<p>ACM/IEEE ANCS is the premier forum for presenting and discussing original research that explores the relationship between the algorithms and architectures of data communication networks and the hardware and software elements from which these networks are built, including both experimental and theoretical analysis.</p> <p>Link: https://ancsconf.org/</p>
18.	International Conference on Vehicle Technology	<p>The purpose of the International Conference on Vehicle Technology and Intelligent Transport Systems (VEHITS) is to bring together engineers,</p>

	and Intelligent Transport Systems (VEHITS)	<p>researchers and practitioners interested in the advances and applications in the field of Vehicle Technology and Intelligent Transport Systems</p> <p>Link: https://vehits.scitevents.org/</p>
19.	IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (IEEE NFV-SDN)	<p>In addition to the latest NFV and SDN concepts and mechanisms, the IEEE NFV-SDN conference focuses on first operational results related to virtualised networks functions (VNFs) as well as designing, describing, orchestrating, and managing new applications made of VNFs which smarten networks and their usage.</p> <p>Link: https://nfvsdn2020.ieee-nfvsdn.org/</p>
20.	IEEE International Conference on Edge Computing (EDGE)	<p>IEEE International Conference on Edge Computing (EDGE) aims to become a prime international forum for both researchers and industry practitioners to exchange the latest fundamental advances in the state of the art and practice of Edge computing, identify emerging research topics, and define the future of Edge computing. EDGE covers the localised resource sharing and connections with the cloud.</p> <p>Link: https://conferences.computer.org/edge/</p>
21.	IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NETSOFT)	<p>NetSoft is dedicated to the theme of Network Softwarisation, involving topics such as Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Network Function Virtualization (NFV), Cloud-Edge-Fog Computing, and Network Automation. It serves as a forum for researchers and international experts to discuss the latest trends, research directions, and leading-edge solution proposals related to this theme.</p> <p>Link: https://netsoft2022.ieee-netsoft.org/</p>
22.	IEEE International Conference on Fog and Edge Computing (ICFEC)	<p>The IEEE International Conference on Fog and Edge Computing seeks to attract high-quality contributions covering both theory and practice over systems research and emerging domain-specific applications related to next-generation distributed systems that use the edge and the fog.</p> <p>Link: https://icfec2022.eecis.udel.edu/</p>
23.	IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)	<p>As the flagship conference of the IEEE Robotics and Automation Society, ICRA brings together the world's top researchers and most important companies to share ideas and advances in the fields of robotics and automation.</p> <p>Link: https://www.ieee-ras.org/conferences-workshops/fully-sponsored/icra</p>

3.2.2. Targeted Scientific Journals and Technical Magazines

5G-IANA will publish its activities and results in scientific peer-reviewed journals and in conference proceedings in order to broadcast its results and get feedback from the scientific and professional community. The consortium will also seek out publication channels in trade journals and magazines to bring out the project's outcomes to end users. All scientific publications stemming from the project research will be made available through green open access and will be uploaded on the website under the Resource page. Some examples of targeted journals and publications are listed in Table 3 below.

Table 3, Targeted Scientific Journals and Technical Magazines

	Journals/Magazines	Themes
1.	IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems	<p>The IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems journal is concerned with the planning, design, management, and the control of future transportation systems requirements conducting both basic and applied research to expand the knowledge base on transportation. This journal serves as a forum for the technological aspects of information technology to transportation, and focuses on the design, analysis, and control of information technology as it is applied to transportation systems.</p> <p>Link: IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems (T-ITS) - IEEE ITSS (ieeetitss.org)</p>
2.	IEEE Communications Magazine	<p>The IEEE Communications Magazine is a monthly magazine published by the IEEE Communications Society dealing with all areas of communications including light-wave telecommunications, high-speed data communications, personal communications systems, and more.</p> <p>Link: IEEE Xplore: IEEE Communications Magazine</p>
3.	IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing	<p>IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing is a bi-monthly peer-reviewed scientific journal covering technology related to the mobility of users, systems, data and computing. It focuses on the key technical issues related to (a) architectures, (b) support services, (c) algorithm/protocol design and analysis, (d)</p>

		<p>mobile environments, (e) mobile communication systems, (f) applications, and (g) emerging technologies.</p> <p>Link: IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing</p>
4.	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications	<p>The IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications publishes high-quality manuscripts on advances in the state-of-the-art of wireless communications. Both theoretical contributions (including new techniques, concepts, and analyses) and practical contributions (including system experiments and prototypes, and new applications) are encouraged.</p> <p>Link: IEEE Xplore: IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications</p>
5.	Elsevier Computer Networks	<p>Computer Networks is an international, archival journal providing a publication vehicle for complete coverage of all topics of interest to those involved in the computer communications networking area. The audience includes researchers, managers and operators of networks as well as designers and implementors.</p> <p>Link: Computer Networks - Journal - Elsevier</p>
6.	Elsevier Computer Communications	<p>Computer Communications is a peer-reviewed international journal that publishes high-quality scientific articles (both theory and practice) and survey papers covering all aspects of future computer communication networks (on all layers, except the physical layer), with a special attention to the evolution of the Internet architecture, protocols, services, and applications.</p> <p>Link: Computer Communications - Journal - Elsevier</p>
7.	Vehicular Communications journal (Elsevier)	<p>The aim of the journal is to publish high quality peer-reviewed papers in the area of vehicular communications. The scope encompasses all types of communications involving vehicles, including vehicle-to-vehicle and vehicle-to-infrastructure.</p> <p>Link: Vehicular Communications - Journal - Elsevier</p>
8.	Telematics and Informatics (Elsevier)	<p>Telematics and Informatics is an interdisciplinary journal publishing innovative theoretical and methodological research on the social, economic, geographic, political, and</p>

		<p>cultural impacts of digital technologies. Application areas include smart cities, sensors and information fusion, the digital society and digital platforms, Internet of Things (IoT), cyber-physical technologies, privacy, knowledge management, distributed work, emergency response and hazards, mobile and wireless communications, health informatics, psychosocial effects of social media, ICT for sustainable development, blockchain, e-commerce, and e-government.</p> <p>Link: Telematics and Informatics - Journal - Elsevier</p>
<p>9.</p>	<p>International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research (Springer)</p>	<p>The International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research aims to provide a global forum for the discussion of effective solutions for intelligent transportation systems, to meet the needs of today's world. It is the only international platform to foster wide-ranging discussions across disciplines by bringing together a broad-based audience for solutions-oriented information and discussion.</p> <p>Link: International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research Home (springer.com)</p>

3.3. Dissemination Activities

This section provides a comprehensive overview of both individual and joint activities that are planned by project partners to take place in the period between October 2022 and the end of the project. This overview derives from the updated individual dissemination plans provided by 5G-IANA partners and consolidated by the Task 7.2 leader (ICCS). The lists of planned dissemination activities presented in Table 4 and Table 5 below are tentative and will be revised closer to the dates, according to both project-related and external needs and developments.

3.3.1. Participation at Events

Table 4 below provides a list of relevant upcoming events and indicative activities as communicated by partners. This list will be continuously updated and extended, and further communicated with 5G-IANA partners to plan the consortium's presence and participation in upcoming events.

Table 4, Participation in Events

Participation in events				
(Conferences, Trade shows, Workshops, Online Events)				
Planned activities				
<i>Period: October 2022 - End of the project</i>				
No.	Name of the event	Date	Place	Activity/Partner (s)
1.	5G-PPP General Assembly 2022	5 - 6 October, 2022	Athens, Greece	Event organisation and presentation (ICCS, NXW)
2.	IZB trade show	11 - 13 October, 2022	Wolfsburg, Germany	Project information (BYL)
3.	IEEE Future Networks Forum 2022: Symposium on 5G for Connected and Automated Mobility	12 - 14 October, 2022	Montreal, Canada (virtual)	Paper Presentation (NXW, UBI, LINKS, ICCS)
4.	TRA 2022	14 - 17 November, 2022	Lisbon, Portugal	Video presentation at the EC Stand (ICCS)
5.	ViSNext'22	6 - 9 December, 2022	Rome, Italy	Part of the organising committee for the 2nd ACM CoNEXT Workshop on Design, Deployment, and Evaluation of Network-assisted Video Streaming (ICCS)
6.	Mobile World Congress	27 February - 2 March, 2023	Barcelona, Spain	TBD (NXW, ICCS)
7.	WCNC 2023	26-29 March, 2023	Glasgow, UK	Paper Presentation (UULM)
8.	IEEE International Conference on Fog and Edge Computing (ICFEC 2023)	24 - 25 April, 2023	New York, USA	Paper Proceedings/ Presentation (NXW, UBI, LINKS, ICCS, NOKIA, ININ, TS)
9.	VEHITS 2023	26 - 28 April, 2023	Prague, Czech Republic	Paper Presentation (VICOM)
10.	NOMS 2023: IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and	8 - 12 May, 2023	Miami, FL, USA	Paper Presentation (UULM)

	Management Symposium			
11.	ITS EU Congress 2023	22 - 24 May, 2023	Lisbon, Portugal	Special Interest Session (ICCS)
12.	ICC 2023	28 May - 01 June, 2023	Rome, Italy	Paper Presentation (UULM)
13.	IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)	29 May - 02 June, 2023	London, UK	Paper/demo/workshop (5COMM)
14.	Vitel, Workshop on Telecommunications	May 2023, May 2024	Brdo pri Kranju, Slovenia	Presenting certain parts of ININ and Ljubljana testbed activities (ININ)
15.	EuCNC 2023	6 - 9 June, 2023	Gothenburg, Sweden	Workshop Organisation/Paper Presentation (ICCS)
Proposal for a workshop on Business aspects along with other projects as part of our involvement in Vision and Societal Working Group/ Presentation of the business-related aspects of 5G-IANA (INC)				
16.	IFIP Networking 2023	12 - 15 June, 2023	Barcelona, Spain	Paper Presentation (UULM)
17.	VTC Spring 2023	18 - 21 June, 2023	Florence, Italy	Paper/demo/workshop (5COMM)
18.	International Electrotechnical and Computer Science Conference ERK	September 2023, September 2024	Portorož, Slovenia	Presenting certain parts of ININ and Ljubljana testbed activities (ININ)
19.	IEEE Future Networks World Forum 2023	TBD	TBD	Workshop on 5G-IANA NetApps' Framework (NXW)
20.	5G ITALY Conference 2023	TBD	Rome, Italy	TBD (NXW)
21.	EuCNC 2024	TBD	TBD	Paper/demo/workshop (5COMM)
22.	Seminar on Radio Communications	February 2023/2024	Ljubljana, SI	Presenting certain parts of ININ and Ljubljana testbed activities (ININ)

23.	ANCS Conference 2024	TBD	TBD	Paper Presentation (UULM)
24.	PAM 2024	TBD	TBD	Paper Presentation (UULM)
25.	ITS European Congress 2024	TBD	TBD	Presentation of the implementation of the LINKS OBU and RSU in the 5G-IANA framework (LINKS)
26.	ISO TC204 Meeting	2 per year	Currently remote, else revolving venues Europe/Americas/Asia-Pacific	Project results for standardisation (FSCOM)
27.	ETSI TC ITS Meeting	4 per year	Currently remote, else Sophia Antipolis, France (ETSI premises)	Project results for standardisation (FSCOM)
28.	ETSI ISG MEC Meeting	4 per year	Currently remote, else varying venues	Project results for standardisation (FSCOM)
29.	Mobile World Congress/2024	TBD	Barcelona, Spain	TBD (NXW)
30.	IoT Week 2024	TBD	TBD	TBD (NXW)
31.	IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (IEEE NFV-SDN)	TBD	TBD	Paper Proceedings/ Presentation (NXW, UBI, LINKS, ICCS)
32.	IEEE International Conference on Edge Computing (EDGE)	TBD	TBD	Paper Proceedings/ Presentation (NXW, UBI, LINKS, ICCS, NOKIA, ININ, TS)
33.	IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NETSOFT)	TBD	TBD	Paper Proceedings/ Presentation (NXW, ICCS)

34.	IEEE International Conference on Fog and Edge Computing (ICFEC 2024)	TBD	TBD	Paper Proceedings/ Presentation (NXW, UBI, LINKS, ICCS, NOKIA, ININ, TS)
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3.3.2. Planned Publications

5G-IANA will leverage conference proceedings, scientific peer-reviewed journals and technical magazines in Europe and beyond to publish papers and articles related to the project’s mission, advancements and results. Table 5 below provides a comprehensive plan, outlining publication opportunities and topics to be elaborated by partners from October 2022 until the end of the project.

Table 5, Planned Publications

Publications (journals, conference proceedings, magazines)				
Planned activities				
<i>Period: October 2022 - End of the project</i>				
No.	Targeted journals / Conferences	Place	Topic planned to be elaborated	Partners Involved
1.	IEEE Internet of Things Magazine ComSoc: Network Application Software for Vertical IoT Industry	n/a	Enabling far-edge intelligent services with NetApps: the Automotive Case	NXW, UBI, LINKS, ICCS, INC
2.	IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems	n/a	Real-synthetic domain alignment for LDM scalability analysis	VICOM, TBD
3.	NOMS 2023	Miami, FL, USA	Explicit congestion monitoring in heterogeneous networks	UULM
4.	EuCNC & 6G Summit 2023	Gothenburg, Sweden	5G-IANA NetApps' Framework	NWX, UBI, Links, ICCS, BYL
			Market analysis, business models, Techno-economic analysis	INC

			NetApp integration - UC demonstration	5GCOMM, TBD
5.	IFIP Networking 2023 (IFIP Digital Library)	Barcelona, Spain	Generating Spatial maps using Federated Learning	UULM
6.	WCNC 2023	Glasgow, UK	QoS estimation using spatial maps and its effect on vehicular applications	UULM
7.	ICC 2023	Rome, Italy	TBD	UULM
8.	ANCS Conference 2024	TBD	In-network processing of network monitoring information	UULM
9.	PAM 2024	TBD	Network measurements and Federated learning using containers on vehicles.	UULM
10.	IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC) Fall 2023 or Spring 2024 Or IEEE Vehicular Networking Conference (VNC) 2023 Or IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC) 2023	TBD	Presentation of the UC "Manoeuvres Coordination for Autonomous Driving"	BYL, NOKIA, 5COMM, NXW, UBI
11.	IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems Or International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research (Springer) Or	TBD	Presentation of the LINKS OBU and RSU in the framework of the 5G-IANA AOEP	NXW, UBI, BYL, ICCS

	Vehicular Communications journal (Elsevier)			
12.	Življenje in tehnika magazine (Life & Technology magazine)	Ljubljana	Automotive technologies and 5G-IANA project overview	TS
13.	TBD	TBD	The cognitive metaverse of connected vehicles	BYL
14.	Workshops at ISO TC204 Meeting	Revolving venues Europe/Americas/Asia-Pacific	Project results and identified standardization gaps	FSCOM, TBD
15.	IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (IEEE NFV-SDN)	TBD	5G-IANA Orchestration Framework	NXW, UBI, LINKS, ICCS
16.	IEEE International Conference on Edge Computing (EDGE)	TBD	5G-IANA solution for Edge orchestration	NXW, UBI, LINKS, ICCS, Nokia, ININ, TS
17.	IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NETSOFT)	TBD	5G-IANA NetApps' Framework and cognitive NetApps	NXW, UBI, ICCS
18.	IEEE International Conference on Fog and Edge Computing (ICFEC)	TBD	5G-IANA solution for Edge orchestration	NXW, UBI, Links, ICCS, Nokia, ININ, TS
19.	EuCNC & 6G Summit 2024	TBD	TBD	NXW, UBI, Links, ICCS, INC, 5GCOMM
20.	IEEE Journal on Robotics and Automation	Journal	NetApp integration - UC demonstration	5COMM, TBD
21.	IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology	Journal	NetApp integration - UC demonstration	5COMM, TBD

22.	Telematics and Informatics	Journal	Market analysis, business models, Techno-economic analysis	INC
23.	Conference of Telecommunication, Media and Internet Techno-Economics (CTTE)	TBD	Market analysis, business models, Techno-economic analysis	INC
24.	Software Networks 5G-PPP WG	White Paper	TBD	NXW
25.	5G Architecture 5G-PPP WG	White Paper	TBD	TBD

3.3.3. 5G-IANA Webinars

Webinars addressing different topics and categories of stakeholders will be organised at regular intervals to provide a comprehensive view of particular results of the project and share key messages and useful information with third-party experimenters. 5G-IANA will organise 9 webinars in total. Five webinars are foreseen to take place in the first years and three more will be organised towards the end of the project (Table 6). Two of them are envisioned to be organised as a joint effort among other ICT-41 projects as well.

Table 6, Webinars' Plan

No.	Date	Webinar Description	Partner(s) Responsible
1.	November 2022	5G-IANA reference architecture and NetApps: Aiming to bridge the gap between the 5G-IANA platform developers and the use case NetApp/VNF developers, and make sure that the latter understand the AOEP concepts and capabilities.	UBI
2.	December 2022 (tentative)	Joint 5G-META and 5G-IANA webinar: Two open platforms that complement each other: How/where to select data (former) vs how/where to select computation (latter). ¹	ICCS
3.	January 2023 (i.e., at the beginning of the Open Call phase of the	Promotion of the 5G-IANA AOEP Release 1 (to give incentives to third-parties): Offered capabilities/facilities and reusable functionalities (e.g., NFs/AFs), description of repositories (NetApp toolkit), type and	ALL

¹ Subject to ongoing discussions among the involved projects.

	engagement workplan)	accessibility of exposed information, open features, KPIs/monitoring options, degrees of freedom given to the experimenters, business-related benefits from using the platform. Emphasise that NOKIA and Telecom Slovenia testbeds will be open for access and explain their facilities' offerings.	
4.	February 2023 (i.e., during the Open Call phase of the engagement workplan)	Presentation of the 5G-IANA test sites at NOKIA and Telecom Slovenia, as well as (autonomous) vehicles / OBUs / RSUs features.	All HW providers
5.	April 2023 (i.e., during the Education & Preparation phase of the engagement workplan)	A user-guide type of webinar, in the form of a how-to-experiment tutorial with hands-on showcasing of the procedure: e.g., demonstration of onboarding NetApps and of the overall platform capabilities. Practical examples of NetApps for the automotive sector, based on the 5G-IANA Use Cases.	NXW
6.	Before ITS European Congress (May 2023)	Joint ICT-41 webinar (5GASP, VITAL-5G, 5G-IANA and 5G-META): "Provision of assets and data in the 5G era". ²	ICCS, UBI
7.	January 2024	Promotion of the 5G-IANA AOEP Release 2	ALL
8.	April 2024	Similar to webinar (5) - updated NetApps examples and how-to-experiment demos	NXW
9.	November 2024	5G-IANA open calls' results and feedback: Lessons learnt from start-ups' and SMEs' integration. Sustainability-related aspects so that platform exploitation is incentivised even after the end of the project.	INC

3.3.4.5G-IANA Videos

5G-IANA's [YouTube channel](#) has already been created to host the project's videos. 5G-IANA will produce 10 videos in total; 3 project-related videos and at least one short video per UC. The first project-related video (M17) is animated and offers a short introduction to the project and its goals. The project's first professional video will launch during TRA 2022 in Lisbon, at the European Commission's stand. The second video is planned for

² Subject to ongoing discussions among the involved projects.

M30 in parallel with the promotion of the project's second Open Call (See 3.3.5), providing a “how-to-experiment tutorial” to the selected SMEs and third-party experimenters and a hands-on showcase of the platform capabilities, together with some practical NetApp examples. The third video will be produced towards the end of the project (M40), summarizing the project's outcomes and including a compilation of the project's 7 use case videos which will be produced during the two (public) demo events.

3.3.5. Stakeholder Engagement: Open Calls and Hackathon

The project will organise two Open Calls for the selection of interested SMEs aiming at testing their innovative automotive solutions and services in the platform developed by 5G-IANA. The project has devised a “third-party engagement plan” that consists of the following 6 distinct phases:

1. Research & Preparation
2. Promotion
3. Open Call
 - a. Submissions
 - b. Evaluation
4. Education & Preparation (pre-testing)
5. Experimentation & Support (validation)
6. Feedback Collection (reporting)

WP7 will be heavily involved in the second and third phases of the ‘third-party engagement plan’ supporting with promotional activities such as the following:

- Assisting with email communications to internal and external stakeholders;
- Providing support in cross-ICT41 project collaboration meetings and other liaison activities;
- Building and executing an online and social media campaign;
- Coordinating and supporting the webinars' organisation;
- Producing and disseminating promotional material about the open calls.

A more detailed presentation of the plan will be available soon in D6.1. According to this plan, we are going to run two Open Calls for SMEs: the first group of SMEs should experiment during M25-M29 and the second one during M35-M39, following Release A and B of the platform, respectively. At the end, three (3) participants will be selected to be granted with a monetary award.

WP7 is currently running the first phase, i.e., creating material to be used during the promotion phase (e.g., website), preparing e-mail templates to be sent out, identifying relevant SMEs to reach out to, and defining the technical and managerial procedures linked to the involvement of third parties, etc.

Moreover, we plan to run the hackathon during M35/M36 to widely disseminate the 5G-IANA solutions to entities willing to enter the Automotive-related 5G-enabled services.

4. CONCLUSION

Deliverable 7.6 outlines the 5G-IANA Dissemination Plan providing a comprehensive framework for future dissemination activities and serving as a helpful manual for all project partners in order to ensure a harmonised and effective project dissemination. The present plan presents the rationale behind the strategy and defines all available means and tools to disseminate the core messages of the project to the right audience.

As previously mentioned, one version has predated the present one. The dissemination plan included within the current document describes planned activities for the period October 2022 to End of the Project. The revised version has incorporated necessary adjustments and additions to best reflect the corrective actions requested by EC experts in the latest review (June 2022).

Dissemination is an integral part of 5G-IANA, as it is essential for the achievement of the project's mission and objectives. Therefore, the contribution of all partners is required (Annex 4 - WP7 Participation per Partner). More specifically, all partners will be asked to support the implementation of the dissemination plan, by contributing into the development of the communication material, providing regular feedback, suggesting local contacts, providing translations and all types of content requested by the Task leader in order to ensure the effectiveness of the strategy. In addition, partners will be responsible and encouraged to attend events that are related to their expertise, keeping in mind the guidelines provided in this document and to disseminate the material in their communications channels, for instance, websites, social media, newsletters, events, etc. The Dissemination Plan is considered as an adaptive live document and it will be further updated when needed according to the different project phases. Moreover, at the time of writing (October 2022), pandemic restrictions are easing up globally, however, it is important to set out alternatives in case COVID-19 negatively affects planned activities. Therefore, further opportunities will be sought in order to promote the project via online events and partners will be encouraged to participate virtually in conferences, webinars, online workshops, etc. Finally, the main objective of this document is to ensure that the project's concept and results are effectively disseminated throughout its lifecycle.

REFERENCES

- [1] «D7.2 Communication strategy and plan,» 5G-IANA, 2022.
- [2] «D7.4 Communication tools,» 5G-IANA, 2022.
- [3] «5G-IANA Website: <https://www.5g-iana.eu/>».
- [4] «5G-IANA LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/5g-iana/>».
- [5] «5G-IANA Twitter: https://twitter.com/IANA_5G».
- [6] «EU Grants: H2020 Guidance — Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects: V1.1 (2020) - Communicating vs Disseminating: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf,» 2020.

ANNEXES

Annex 1 – Dissemination and Approval Procedure

Dissemination activities such as journal publications and conference papers require internal approval by the consortium. Partners should inform the Dissemination Manager about all upcoming activities such as conference presentations, paper submissions etc. two weeks prior to the activity using the dissemination form that will be provided (Annex 2).

The participation of any partner in an event, the publication or presentation of work done within the framework of 5G-IANA or the performance of any other dissemination activity related to the project has to be approved beforehand by the 5G-IANA Consortium. The dissemination procedure is to be followed by **all partners** equally, in order to:

- Produce high quality 5G-IANA publications and presentations;
- Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Efficiently monitor, record and promote the dissemination activities of the project;
- Secure the brand identity of the project and the EC rules to be followed.

The WP7 leader (VICOM) and the Task 7.2 leader (ICCS) are responsible for ensuring compliance with the procedures. All partners are called to contribute efficiently on the dissemination of the project.

Step by step procedure

Before the performance of any dissemination activity related to the 5G-IANA project, **the initiator of the dissemination activity** should:

STEP 1: If applicable, store the material (abstract, draft paper, poster etc.) on Redmine, on the *WP7 Dissemination folder* and specifically the *In Progress* sub-folder;

STEP 2: Inform by e-mail the Task 7.2 Leader (Sevi Christoforou) for the intention to participate on a dissemination activity with a link to the stored material and/or a table with the following information: a) title of the dissemination activity, b) a short description (up to 150 words) and its relation to the 5G-IANA project;

STEP 3: Task 7.2 leader has 2 days to react and send the request to the Consortium for approval, modification or rejection;

STEP 4: The Consortium decision and comments should be sent to the Task 7.2 leader within five working days; If no answer is received due to the set deadline, it is taken as an approval;

STEP 5: Task 7.2 leader informs the involved partner(s) about the decision.

In case of:

- a) **Approval:** The initiator may proceed with the submission or realization of the planned dissemination activity;
- b) **Conflict/objection:** Any Consortium member can object to the proposed dissemination activity, for example in cases of overlaps or risk of disclosure of restricted or confidential information. **The objection has to include a clear reasoning as well as a precise request for necessary modifications.**

The issue is discussed among the Coordinator, the Task 7.2 Leader and the involved partners.

Dissemination Activities report

Within **ten working days** after the realization of the dissemination activity, the partner should provide the Task 7.2 Leader with the filled in dissemination report (the dissemination report will soon be available on Redmine) and the presented dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.). It will be also appreciated if the lead partner of every dissemination activity provides the WP7 Leader and Task 7.2 Leader with some photos of the participation at the event. The partners are requested to complete all the fields briefly and clearly, trying to avoid the use of abbreviations.

The filled in report, as well as all the material received, will be archived by ICCS to the Dissemination Activity Inventory on Redmine.

Acknowledgement

Any communication and dissemination activity related to the project, as well as any infrastructure, equipment must:

- Display the EU emblem and
- Include the acknowledgment text

The following acknowledgement text should be included in all communication activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016427”.

The following acknowledgement text should be included for infrastructure, equipment and major results:

“This [infrastructure][equipment] [insert type of result] is part of 5G-IANA project that has received funding from the European Union’ s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016427”.

Disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility

Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that:

“It reflects only the author’s view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

For correct use of the EC emblem please use the following link: European emblem: https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/symbols/european-flag_en

For further information please contact the Task 7.2 Leader **Sevi Christoforou**.

Dissemination Request Table

TITLE:	
Description / Short Summary	

**Relation to
5G-IANA**

Annex 2 – Dissemination Activities Report template

The dissemination activities report should be filled in by the leading partner of every realised dissemination activity. The purpose of this report is to provide the necessary information to the Task 7.2 Leader for publishing the activity to the 5G-IANA website and for reporting to the European Commission.

In case of Events (i.e. Project Events, Conference Presentations, Exhibitions etc.)	
Title of event / place & date of realisation:	
Type of Event:	Conference, Workshop, technical meeting etc.
Title of presentation:	
Type of presentation:	poster presentation, paper presentation, demo presentation, oral presentation...
Relevance to 5G-IANA:	Please specify: WPx work, concept description etc.
Author(s)/ Presenter(s):	Name (company)
Other activities (if any)	i.e. distribution of promotional material, bilateral discussions etc.
Type of audience addressed (event/meeting)	Scientific community (higher education, research)
	Industry
	Civil society
	Policy makers / Public authorities
	Media
	Other: please specify
In case of an Event:	NATIONAL: hosting country: <input type="text"/> → Number of attendees: <input type="text"/>
	INTERNATIONAL: hosting country: <input type="text"/> → addressed countries: <input type="text"/> → Number of overall attendees: <input type="text"/> → Size of audience addressed by the performed activity: <input type="text"/>
	Liaison with relevant actors: no, yes: partners, projects, initiatives, shared session? <input type="text"/> . Any feedback received? no, yes: Please specify.
In case of a meeting:	LOCAL → Number of attendees: <input type="text"/> NATIONAL: hosting country: <input type="text"/> → Number of attendees: <input type="text"/> INTERNATIONAL: addressed countries: <input type="text"/> → Number of attendees: <input type="text"/> Main purpose of the meeting: <input type="text"/> / Relevance to 5G-IANA: <input type="text"/> Related contacts made: <input type="text"/> / Feedback received: <input type="text"/> Do you foresee further involvement of the actors you met with? <input type="text"/>

In case of Scientific Publications (Conference papers, journals / magazines, book chapter etc.)	
Type of publication	journal article, conference paper, book chapter etc.
Main Author (name, organisation)	<input type="text"/>
Title of publication:	<input type="text"/>
Relevance to 5G-IANA:	Please specify: WPx work, concept description etc.
Other Authors:	<input type="text"/>
In case of a journal/magazine article:	Title of journal or magazine: <input type="text"/>
	Volume, page: <input type="text"/>
	Editor / Publisher: <input type="text"/>
	ISSN: <input type="text"/>
In case of a Conference paper:	Title of proceedings <input type="text"/>
	Editor/publisher: <input type="text"/>
In case of a book publication:	Title of book: <input type="text"/>
	Title of Chapter: <input type="text"/>
	Editor / Publisher: <input type="text"/>
	Pages: <input type="text"/>
	ISBN: <input type="text"/>
For all publications:	Date of publication: <input type="text"/>
	URL (if available) <input type="text"/>
	DOI number <input type="text"/>
	Open access to publication? <input type="text"/> no yes: (way to get it)
	Additional info: <input type="text"/>

Other activities	
Type of activity:	i.e. video presentation, event organisation, website announcement, press briefings, interviews etc.
Title:	<input type="text"/>
Occasion:	Name of Event/ publication etc.
URL:	<input type="text"/>
Relevance to 5G-IANA:	<input type="text"/>

Partners Involved:	<input type="text"/>
Short description:	<input type="text"/>
Other Comments:	<input type="text"/>

For all dissemination activities		
Presented material (<i>Full paper/article/poster/ presentation, etc.</i>)	Attached to this form	<input type="text"/>
	Link to Redmine	<input type="text"/>
Permission to publish the material in the 5G-IANA website:	YES	<input type="text"/>
	NO	<input type="text"/>
Other Comments:	<input type="text"/>	

Annex 3 – WP7 tasks and leaders

Task & Leader	Task Descriptions
<p>Task 7.1: Communication strategy and tools</p> <p>Leader: VICOM</p>	<p>Define the overall dissemination and communication strategy to be followed so as to efficiently promote 5G-IANA and its results to the different target audiences. Communication and dissemination strategy and plan will incorporate the specific messages to be targeted at specified audiences, through appropriate channels, taking into account their needs and concerns and will serve as a guide for the consortium to effectively allocate time and resources and maximise project impact. The main communication tools will be also produced and high impact communication activities will be deployed so as to achieve wide awareness on 5G-IANA objectives and results. The 5G-IANA main activities/communication tools, are the following: branding, website and social media accounts, a communication kit to facilitate the information flow and promotion of the project to a wider audience and at events i.e., a flagship flyer, an e-newsletter, short videos, a set of 5G-IANA roll-up banners and one professional video.</p>
<p>Task 7.2: Dissemination activities and events</p> <p>Leader: ICCS</p>	<p>Ensure that the 5G-IANA results are systematically disseminated to the expert communities and to relevant stakeholders throughout the lifetime of the project and increase the reach and impact of the project. Organise the presentation of 5G-IANA activities and results in conferences and other events, through special sessions, oral and poster presentations and workshops. Ensure the production and publication of scientific and technical papers from the 5G-IANA experts in conference proceedings and top ranked peer-reviewed scientific and technology journals. Organise demonstration events and press conferences, for each 5G-IANA demonstration activity and during some targeted international conferences and trade fairs.</p>
<p>Task 7.3: Liaison activities and international cooperation</p> <p>Leader: LINKS</p>	<p>Plan and execute 5G-IANA liaison activities with related EU and international R&D initiatives, policy makers and related organisations and networks, to widely promote project's results. Creation of synergies with past and future R&D projects and liaison with already established networks, associations, organisations as well as related fora and technical communities. Coordinate with other relevant actors from the ongoing 5G-PPP projects. Provide inputs to relevant working groups and special interest groups within 3GPP through 5G-IANA partners who are 3GPP members. Develop cooperation agreements with the international 5G community, for instance 5G-IA, 5G Forum (Korea), 5G MF (Japan), 5G Americas as well as other fora (e.g., 5GAA).</p>
<p>Task 7.4: Exploitation strategy</p> <p>Leader: INC</p>	<p>Define the necessary methodology, metrics and templates for the preparation of homogeneous and effective exploitation plans of 5G-IANA. Outline specific business metrics for analysing the exploitation potential of the partners' ideas, to define legal rights and obligations in the exploitation process, to set the precise procedure to be followed in order to define and agree upon IP Rights of each partner and to include templates and procedures to be followed in order to elaborate the individual exploitation</p>

	plans, which will be prepared by each of the participants on a regular yearly basis.
<p>Task 7.5: Standardisation, EU policies and regulations</p> <p>Leader: FSCOM</p>	Provide recommendations and requirements to standardisation work groups and EU/global policymakers in the telecommunications and transport domains based on results of relevant WPs and the validation of the demonstrations. Propose recommendations to regulatory authorities based on the outcomes of the telecom part of the project, i.e., the specification of policies relevant to the exploitation of 5G (including specific channels) for the demonstration-oriented solutions.

Annex 4 - WP7 Participation per Partner

All partners will participate in the activities of WP7 and the dissemination of 5G-IANA results. VICOM, WP7 Leader, is also leader of Task 7.1 Communication strategy and tools. ICCS will lead Task 7.2, Dissemination activities and events, will organise the final event together with a Hackathon and will participate in the rest of the WP7 tasks. LINKS leads Task 7.3 Liaison activities and international cooperation while INCITES leads Task 7.4 Exploitation strategy and FSCOM leads Task 7.5 Standardisation, EU policies and regulations; all of them will have a major role in all WP7 activities.

Allocated effort per partner is described in the below:

Partner	WP7 effort
1 - ICCS	13.00
2 - NOKIA	8.00
3 - UULM	3.00
4 - LINKS	8.00
5 - VICOM	10.00
6 - TS	8.00
7 - UBI	7.00
8 - HIT	6.00
9 - BYL	6.00
10 - FSCOM	7.00
11 - NXW	5.00
12 - 5COMM	5.00
13 - INC	7.00
14 - O7	4.00
15 - COGN	6.00
16 - ININ	4.00
Total	107.00

Annex 5 – WP7 Deliverables

No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dis. Level	Due date (in months)
D7.1	Brand identity and guidelines	5 - VICOM	Websites, patents filling, etc	Public	6
D7.2	Communication strategy and plan	5 - VICOM	Report	Public	9
D7.3	Communication strategy and plan V2	5 - VICOM	Report	Public	21
D7.4	Communication tools	5 - VICOM	Websites, patents filling, etc	Public	9
D7.5	Communication tools V2	5 - VICOM	Websites, patents filling, etc	Public	21
D7.6	Dissemination plan	1 - ICCS	Report	Public	9
D7.7	Exploitation plan	13 - INC	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	18
D7.8	Report on the dissemination activities	1 - ICCS	Report	Public	42
D7.9	Report on international cooperation and liaison activities	4 - LINKS	Report	Public	42
D7.10	Exploitation report	13 - INC	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	42
D7.11	Standardisation activities, EU	10 - FSCOM	Report	Public	42

	policies and regulations recommendations				
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Annex 6 – List of Performed Activities

Paper Publications

No.	Title	Authors	Partner(s)	Journal	Status
1.	A Distributed ML Framework for Service Deployment in the 5G-based Automotive Vertical	Vasilis Sourlas, Amr Rizk, Konstantinos V. Katsaros, Panagiotis Pantazopoulos, Georgios Drainakis and Angelos Amditis	ICCS, UULM	The International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking 2021. IEEE MeditCom	Published
2.	5G-IANA: A 5G Experimentation Platform for Intelligent Automotive Network Applications	V. Sourlas, K. V. Katsaros, A. Xirofotos, D. Klonidis, E. Bonetto, D. Brevi, R. Scopigno, F. Moscatelli, M. Wimmer, B. Haetty, S. Schulz, A. Rizkk, M. Buchholz and A. Amditis	ICCS, UBITECH, LINKS, NXW, NOKIA, UULM	IEEE 5G for CAM Virtual Summit	Published
3.	On the Resource Consumption of Distributed ML	G. Drainakis, P. Pantazopoulos, K. V. Katsaros, V. Sourlas, and A. Amditis	ICCS	IEEE International Symposium on Local and Metropolitan Area Networks (IEEE LANMAN 2021)	Published
4.	Resource Allocation for Distributed Machine Learning at the (Edge-Cloud) Continuum	Ippokratis Sartzetakis, Polyzois Soumplis, Panagiotis Pantazopoulos and, Konstantinos V. Katsaros, Vasilis Sourlas and Emmanouel Varvarigos	ICCS	IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC): Communication, QoS, Reliability and Modeling Symposium (IEEE ICC'22 - CQRM Symposium)	Published
5.	The 5G-IANA platform: Bringing far-edge resources and ML potential to the disposal of automotive third parties	Francesca Moscatelli, Thanos Xirofotos, Amr Rizk, Nehal Baganal-Krishna, Edoardo Bonetto, Eirini Liotou, Angelos Amditis	NXW, UBI, LINKS, ICCS	IEEE Future Networks Forum 2022: Symposium on 5G for Connected and Automated Mobility	Accepted

6.	Enabling far-edge intelligent services with NetApps: the Automotive Case	K. V. Katsaros, E. Liotou, F. Moscatelli, T. Rokkas, E. Bonetto, D. Brevi, D. Klonidis, and A. Amditis	ICCS, NXW, UBI, LINKS	IEEE Internet of Things Magazine ComSoc: Network Application Software for Vertical IoT Industry	Under minor revision
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Technical & Scientific Papers

No.	Title	Authors	Partner(s) Involved	Occasion	Status
1.	From 5G to 6G Vision - A Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) perspective	Joint White Paper	LINKS, ICCS,	6G IA 5G for CAM Working Group	Published
2.	NetApp: Opening up 5G and beyond networks - 5G-PPP projects analysis	Joint White Paper	NXW	Software Networks 5G-PPP WG	Published

Participation at Conferences and External Events

No.	Event	Type of Activity	Partner(s) Involved	Year
1.	IEEE 5G for CAM (Virtual)	Paper presentation	ICCS	2021
2.	ITS EU Congress (Toulouse, France)	SIS organisation & presentation	ICCS, ININ, LINKS	2022
3.	EuCNC & 6G Summit (Grenoble, France)	SIS presentation	NXW, ICCS	2022
4.	4 th Summit on Gender Equality in Computing (Thessaloniki, Greece)	Poster presentation	ICCS, UULM	2022
5.	IEEE MeditCom 2022 (Athens, Greece)	Workshop Presentation	ICCS	2022
6.	5G-PPP GA Meeting (Athens, Greece)	Joint presentation with VITAL-5G	NXW	2022
7.	IEEE Future Networks Forum 2022: Symposium on 5G for Connected and Automated Mobility (Montreal CA, hybrid)	Paper Presentation	UBI	2022
8.	ViSNext'22 (Rome, Italy)	Event Co-chair Keynote speech	ICCS	2022

Exhibition booths

No.	Event	Type of Activity	Partner(s) Involved	Year
1.	Connecting Europe Days (Lyon, France)	Exhibition booth	ICCS	2022
2.	TRA 2022 (Lisbon, Portugal)	Exhibition booth (presence at EC stand/video launch)	ICCS	2022

Other Dissemination Activities

No.	Type of Activity/Event	Partner(s) Involved	Year
1.	5G-IANA in 5G-PPP Brochure, https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/5GPPP_Phase3_Brochure_WEB-1.pdf	ICCS	2022
2.	Project Presentation at booth during VTM 2022 (Turin, Italy)	BYL	2022
3.	Organisation of the 5G-PPP GA Meeting in Athens	ICCS	2022
4.	Project Presentation at booth during IZB Fair 2022 (Wolfsburg, Germany)	BYL	2022